

Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan (DMP)

Project:
SUMCASTEC

Abstract: The **SUMCASTEC** project develops the first lab-on-chip platform for isolation and neutralization of cancer stem cells (CSCs). The purpose of data collection within the project is therefore validation of a novel technology and ultimately development of new treatment approaches for brain tumours such as Glioblastoma Multiforme and Medulloblastoma.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) within the project is a part of the Horizon 2020 pilot action called Open Research Data (ORD) pilot in which SUMCASTEC participates. This document describes the **initial Data Management Plan (DMP)** for SUMCASTEC and is based on the Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020 document version 3.0 of 26 July 2016.

*“A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by a Horizon 2020 project. As part of making research data **findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR)**, a DMP should include information on:*

- *the handling of research data during and after the end of the project*
- *what data will be collected, processed and/or generated*
- *which methodology and standards will be applied*
- *whether data will be shared/made open access and*
- *how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).*

A DMP is required for all projects participating in the extended ORD pilot, unless they opt out of the ORD pilot”.

ADMIN Details

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Scientific coordinator	A. Pothier, University of Limoges
Admin contact	G. Feat, University of Limoges gaelle.feat@unilim.fr
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Projects participating in the pilot must submit a first version of the DMP (as a deliverable) within the first 6 months of the project. The DMP needs to be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise.

Further details are provided in the [Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020](#) (v.3, 26 July 2016).

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Section 1: Data summary

1.1 Purpose of the data collection/generation and relation to the objectives of the project

The purpose of data collection/generation is to gather evidence that the developed lab-on-chip platform can isolate and neutralize CSCs, which will require characterization of the new device performance along with characterization of the biological response of the samples tested (ex. cells) using the device. Additionally it will be necessary to collect data from biological cells tested and characterized without utilizing the developed device (ex. by traditional petri dishes culture) in order to benchmark the novel technology/procedures against established “gold” standards.

Therefore the collected data will include the experimental procedures for characterization of the device along with the protocols for biological testing. Finally, simulation data and code, for example for automatic control of measurement instruments, will be also collected.

1.2 Types and formats of the data

The data will be collected in text, numerical and image formats and gathered in files whose extension are defined by the equipment/software used for generation and collection. Some examples include but are not limited to .xlsx (Excel spreadsheet), .ppt(PowerPoint), .mat (Matlab), .txt (text), .s2p (touchstone), .avi (video). Data will be generated by individuals or groups of researchers in all involved institutions.

1.3 Size of the data

The expected size cannot be predicted at this stage but it is reasonable to assume that it will hit the tens of Gigabyte range.

1.4 Targeted users of the collected data

The data will be useful to members of the scientific community who are willing to reproduce and build on the described experiments or develop similar technologies.

Section 2: FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

Considering the strongly interdisciplinary nature of the project SUMCASTEC's consortium favors the adoption of a broad and domain agnostic metadata standard that the EU recommends to its member states for recording information about research activity: the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) standard is described at <http://www.eurocris.org/cerif/main-features-cerif>

An additional advantage of a CERIF inspired standard is that SUMCASTEC's DMP managing institution (Bangor University) currently uses a research information system developed by Elsevier that implements the CERIF standard (PURE).

2.1.1 Identifiability of data

For publication data unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers will be used. For other data the identification mechanism described in "Naming and convention used" will be adopted.

2.1.1 Naming and conventions used

The following structure is proposed for a SUMCASTEC data set identifier:

"Project"_"Date"_"Time"_"Name"_"Type"_"Extension"_"Place"_"Creators"_"Target user"_"Other"

Where:

- "Project" is the project name (SUMCASTEC by default).
- "Date" is the date in format "YYMMDD" which is chosen to allow data that was taken at similar dates to be stored in close locations. For the same reason the date and time fields are set to precede the name field.
- "Time": is the time in format "HHMMSS" if relevant, or NA by default.
- "Name" is a short name for the data.
- "Type" describes the type of data (e.g. publication, measured data, simulation data, protocol description ...).
- "Extension" describes the data file extension.
- "Place" describes the location where the data were produced.
- "Creators" defines the individual(s) who generated the data.
- "Target user" defines the target audience of the data, if known.

- “Other” is an optional field for additional details (whose default value is NA).

For example:

“SUMCASTEC”_“170519”_“092134”_“Sparameters”_“Measured”_“txt”_“Bangor”_“Cr C. Palego”_“Partners and public”_“NA”

is a file named Sparameters that was taken on May 19th 2017 at 9:21 AM and contains measured data with txt extension. Such data was generated in Bangor by C. Palego and its storage target SUMCASTEC partners as well as general public. A simple excel spreadsheet has been created and will be distributed to all partners for a highly automatized generation of file names using the described format. An example of the file name generated using such a tool is visible in figure 1.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Field	Entry			Notes					
2	Project	SUMCASTEC		–						
3	Date	170519		–	Year Month Day format! Ex. 170519 for the 19th of May 2017					
4	Time	092134		–	24h format. Type NA if not relevant					
5	Name	Sparameters		–						
6	Type	Measured data		–	Ex. publication, measured data, code, protocol, ...					
7	Extension	txt		–	File extension if known					
8	Place	Bangor		–	You can specify additional details such as particular lab					
9	Creator(s)	C. Palego		–						
10	Target User	Partners and public		–						
11	Other	NA			If you want to add anything else					
12										
13	File Name:	SUMCASTEC_170519_092134_Sparameters_Measured data_txt_Bangor_C. Palego_Partners and public_NA								
14		<i>(Cell D12 is the recommended file name for uploading to Zenodo repository.</i>								
15		<i>You can copy and paste it to any other document,</i>								
16		<i>but please do not mess with its definition in this file!)</i>								

Figure 1: simple Excel utility to be distributed to all partners for generation of data name according to the DMP convention.

2.1.2 Approach towards keywords

For publication data the official keywords list provided by the publisher will be used. For other data keywords will be selected by the data owner.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1. Data to be made publicly available and rationale for keeping some data closed

Publications: Partners will be free to publish and disseminate their own results according to the procedure defined and agreed in the Consortium Agreement. The consortium will comply with the Grant Agreement open access clause for the publications generated from the project, but will deposit them into institutional (closed) repositories like the University of Limoges’ Ucloud (<https://ucloud.unilim.fr>) before moving them to public data repositories like Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>). The timing and approach in moving publications to the public repository is similar to those for the other data and is discussed in next session.

Other data: SUMCASTEC's partners strive for maximum openness of data collected

and generated during the project but reserve the right to evaluate which data will be made publicly available along with the time for publication on a case by case basis. The "Guidelines for FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" recognize the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialization and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions. It is expected that the dominant causes for enforcing data access restriction during SUMCASTEC will be protection of IPR and commercialization strategies. It is also expected that the openness stance regarding individual items can be reviewed and updated periodically. For example, test results or experimental protocols can be made publicly available after the consortium has filed for the corresponding patents.

The decision as to data openness and availability time will be made through a vote held by the steering board. If the amount and quality of data is deemed to require an extraordinary board consultation, a meeting will be scheduled at the earliest convenience. Otherwise the steering board will hold a vote in the frame of the scheduled consortium meetings.

2.2.2. Methods to access the data

SUMCASTEC has chosen the Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) repository for storing the project data and a SUMCASTEC project account has been thereby created. Zenodo is a repository supported by CERN and the EU OpenAire project, is open, free, searchable and structured with flexible licensing allowing for storing all types of data: datasets, images, presentations, publications and software. Additionally:

- The repository has backup and archiving capabilities.
- The repository allows for integration with github.com³ (a platform providing a free and flexible tool for code developing and storage) which could be used for storing of code generated during the project (ex. code for data analysis and automated measurement setup drivers).
- The repository can be set to restrict access to the data under embargo status until a chosen date; then the content becomes publically available automatically.
- Zenodo assigns all publicly available uploads a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make the upload easily and uniquely citable.

Finally, the documentation about the software needed to access the data will be included by means of a text file that will be periodically updated.

2.2.2. Restricted area access

If an embargo is sought to give the consortium time to publish or seek IPR protection, data will be accessible through Zenodo.org to consortium members only until the agreed embargo expiration date.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.2.1. Data interoperability and used vocabulary

The depositors will strive for adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications as from the CERIF guidelines. They will also strive for using a standard vocabulary for all data types present to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

2.4.1. Data licensing

The flexible licensing capability embedded in Zenodo will be leveraged to partition the repository space in an open area and a restricted access area with the aim to transfer as much data as possible to the open area at the earliest convenience. Sharing of data with restricted access will be possible only by the depositor's approval.

2.4.2. Reusability at the end of the project

The data produced and/or used in the project will be useable by third parties, both during and after the end of the project as far as it is placed in the open area of the Zenodo repository. Access by third parties will be encouraged through dissemination initiatives for example by sharing the repository address and basic access instructions during conference presentations.

2.4.3. Data quality assurance process

The DMP manager will periodically assess compliance of the repository entries to the preset format and content standards. The Plan is a living document whose content concerning the data management will be updated from its creation (month 6 of the project) to the end of the project (month 42).

2.4.4. Re-usability duration

The length of time for which the data will remain re-usable will not be enforced by SUMCASTEC partners after the end of the project (unless it is deemed that further IPR protection steps need to be taken). However it is foreseeable that re-usability will depend on the demonstrated technology obsolescence.

Section 3: Allocation of resources

The chosen repository (ZENODO) is free of charge for educational and informational use. While no resources were specifically devoted to making SUMCASTEC's data FAIR, all partner institutions have budgeted dissemination costs supporting Open access publication. Therefore they will make sure that peer-reviewed journal article they publish is openly accessible, free of charge (article 29.2. Model Grant Agreement). <http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=openaccess>

For some publishers supporting a green route to Open Access of journals, special issues and conference proceedings a post-print version of the publication will be made available in the Zenodo repository. This version is after the peer-review changes have been made, but it does not typically include the publication-specific formatting. This version may also be referred to as the author's final draft, accepted author manuscript (AAM) or the author's final peer-reviewed manuscript.

For example the IEEE supports this green route to Open Access for the IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques.

Section 4: Data security

4.1 Data recovery

By relying on the ZENODO repository SUMCASTEC's research output will be stored safely in the same cloud infrastructure as research data from CERN's Large Hadron Collider and using CERN's battle-tested repository software INVENIO (a fully customised digital library framework).

All files uploaded to Zenodo are stored in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers.

4.2 Secure storage

Metadata and persistent identifiers in Zenodo are stored in a PostgreSQL instance operated on CERN's Database on Demand infrastructure with 12-hourly backup cycle with one backup sent to tape storage once a week.

4.1 Transfer of sensitive data

Transfer of sensitive data will occur uniquely from the University of Limoges cloud infrastructure (Ucloud) that the consortium has chosen for internal data storage and transfer.

Section 5: Ethical aspects

The ethics aspects have been covered in the proposal and by obtaining (a) any ethics committee opinion required under national law and (b) any notification or authorization for activities raising ethical issues required under national and/ or European law.

The documents submitted upon request by the coordinator to the Agency will be added to the Zenodo repository.

Section 6: Use of the DMP within the project

The plan is used by the SUMCASTEC partners as a reference for data management (naming, providing metadata, storing and archiving) within the project each time new project data are produced.

The project partners are introduced to the DMP and its use as part of WP5 activities. Relevant questions from partners will be specifically addressed within WP5. The workpackage will also provide support to the project partners on using Zenodo as the data management tool.

Section 7: List of acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
CSCs	Cancer Stem Cells
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable
LOC	Lab-on-chip
ORD	Open Research Data